

6G Wireless Communications for Industrial Automation: Scenarios, Requirements and Challenges

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Abstract

Industrial automation is an essential part of modern industries, including manufacturing and utilities, driven by the need to enhance productivity, precision and efficiency. This paper provides a comprehensive review of recent advances in industrial automation, focusing on the role of 6G wireless communication as a key enabler. We explore various categorizations and reference use cases within industrial automation and show how 6G technology can meet the evolving needs of these environments. The functional, service and non-functional system requirements needed to support these advanced automation scenarios are also outlined. A critical analysis of the challenges associated with the application of 6G technology in industry is presented, highlighting technical, operational and implementation barriers. At the end of the paper, we also discuss the key lessons learned from the efforts to date and suggest future directions for research and development to address the aforementioned challenges. By addressing various complex issues, this paper aims to provide a clear path for the integration of next-generation communication technologies into industrial automation systems.

Keywords: use cases, industrial automation, requirements, 6G

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1. Introduction

In the era of Industry 4.0, the manufacturing landscape is undergoing a profound transformation, characterized by a heightened emphasis on automation and digitization. The journey from ISA-95 to the RAMI 4.0, alongside the adoption of the Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA), continues to reshape industrial processes [1]. This transformation extends to the integration of traditional OT with modern ICT solutions. As depicted in Figure 1, the traditional paradigm of industrial mass production, primarily aimed at achieving economies of scale, is evolving toward mass customization and personalization due mainly to consumers desiring to influence and participate in the various designs of the products they use. Thus, this transformation can be mapped to an axis of model volume expansion and the change in the variety of these models as shown in the same figure.

Figure 1: Mass production evolution to personalized production and objectives of the manufacturing paradigms.

This evolution also entails the production of a myriad of individualized products tailored to diverse consumer needs [2]. Industrial automation is pivotal to this shift, driven by an ecosystem that incorporates industrial robots, advanced networked devices, and cutting-edge technologies such as AI, the IoT, and data

engineering. This convergence of technology and stakeholder collaboration enables personalization and value differentiation. The proliferation of industrial robots, as projected by experts [3], underlines the ongoing growth in automation. However, this growth introduces multifaceted considerations, including connectivity, infrastructure, security, cyber-physical systems, and human involvement. Furthermore, implementation frameworks and platforms are still at an early stage of development.

In recent years, industrial automation has become increasingly ubiquitous, promising improvements in efficiency, accuracy, and production quality. It also offers the potential for cost savings, lower labor costs and greater precision in manufacturing processes. 5G, on the other hand, is already having an impact on industrial automation. For example, BMW uses 5G to control robots and other machines in its factories¹. This has helped BMW reduce production time and improve quality. Siemens is using 5G to develop new applications for industrial automation, such as predictive maintenance and remote control². 5G has reduced the latency of communications between machines and devices in the smart factory and is a more reliable communications technology than previous generations of cellular networks³, [4]. 5G has also made it easier to reconfigure factory layouts and add new machines and equipment⁴. On the other hand, while 5G technology has already found applications in various industrial sectors, including smart factories, industrial IoT, AR and VR in manufacturing, and predictive maintenance [5, 6], it still struggles with some challenges.

¹Online: <https://www.press.bmwgroup.com/global/article/detail/T0298955EN/5g-mobile-network-goes-live-at-all-bmw-brilliance-automotive-production-sites-in-china?language=en>, Available: September 2023.

²Online: <https://www.siemens.com/global/en/products/automation/industrial-communication/industrial-5g.html>, Available: September 2023

³Online: <https://www.ericsson.com/en/cases/2020/accelerate-factory-automation-with-5g-urllc>, Available: September 2023.

⁴Online: <https://www.nxp.com/company/blog/flex-your-factory-5g-and-wireless-technologies-bring-greater-flexibility-and-mobility-to-smart-factories:BL-FLEX-YOUR-FACTORY>, Available: September 2023

40 These challenges include limitations in reliability, capacity, coverage, and security, which hinders the ability to fully meet the communication requirements of industrial automation.

1.1. *The Potential Impact of 6G*

Mobile robots, AGV, XR (an emerging umbrella term for all the immersive
45 technologies (VR, AR, and MR)), digital twins, IVC, and other new concepts are also related to the communications for industrial automation in that they require reliable and efficient communication networks to function effectively. In many cases, these technologies rely on real-time data and feedback to operate, which means that they require low latency and high bandwidth connections.
50 For example, mobile robots and AGV rely on communication networks to receive commands, navigate their surroundings, and report their progress back to central control systems.

These systems often require high levels of reliability to ensure that the robots are able to navigate safely and avoid collisions with other objects or people.
55 They can enable remote communication and collaboration between workers and teams across different locations, which can improve efficiency and productivity in industrial settings. For example, mobile robots equipped with cameras and sensors can be remotely controlled to perform tasks in hazardous environments (e.g., for tasks such as assembly, welding, and packaging), while workers can
60 monitor and control their actions from a safe location.

It is in this context that the focus of our research turns to 6G cellular systems. Due to its ability to transmit large amounts of data quickly and reliably, 6G-based wireless communications are expected to play a major role in industrial automation. 6G holds promise as a communication technology that can
65 facilitate robust communication between production machines, robots, and software, offering faster and more reliable data transmission. Additionally, 6G can empower industrial automation systems to seamlessly integrate sensors, controllers, and human-machine interfaces, thereby enhancing control, monitoring, and optimization of production processes.

70 6G wireless systems will enable remote control and monitoring of production machines and robots, as well as remote access to production data. This brings new requirements, uncovered scenarios, and relevant industrial applications for the integration of wireless and industrial technologies, especially for both IT and OT communication. The goal of 6G wireless systems in the 3GPP Rel-19 or
75 Rel-20 [7] is envisioned as to include not only the traditional uRLLC scenarios, but also future scenarios such as the Internet of Robots, holographic/semantic communications, drone taxi, etc., to support the industrial sector and the demanding use cases in factories (which require higher throughput (i.e., $100\times$), lower latency (i.e., 100 microseconds at peak) and higher penetration per square
80 kilometer ($10\times$) compared to 5G) until 2030 (see Table 2 for details [7]).

Manufacturing scheduling [8] in complex environments can benefit greatly from 6G technology as it enables real-time data integration, energy-efficient operation and advanced predictive maintenance. By leveraging the 6G's uRLLC, manufacturers can dynamically adjust their schedules, optimize energy con-
85 sumption and improve the overall equipment effectiveness. Service scheduling [9] can also be transformed by 6G technology, with real-time connectivity and AI-driven decision support enabling dynamic rerouting, sophisticated scheduling algorithms and improved client communication. This will optimize the coordination of resources, improve service quality and ensure timely adjustments to
90 schedules based on real-time conditions.

Table 1 provides an overview of existing survey papers and studies related to 6G and its applications in industrial automation. It includes references to papers published between 2019 and 2023, covering various focus areas such as 6G implementation challenges, routing and scheduling optimization, intelligent
95 automation, and the role of 6G in Industry 4.0.

1.2. Main Contributions

In 6G system various surveys and reviews already exist, but lacks industrial aspects. For example, the authors in [19] provide a comprehensive survey of the current developments towards 6G. The paper in [10] aims to provide a compre-

TABLE 1
SUMMARY OF EXISTING STUDIES ON 6G IN INDUSTRIAL AUTOMATION

Reference	Year	Focus Area	Methodology	Key Findings
Jiang et al. [10]	2021	6G Applications	Roadmap	This survey provides a broad overview of 6G technologies, covering potential applications, key challenges, and enabling technologies.
Fu et al., [9]	2023	Routing	Optimization	Multi-objective optimization approach for routing and scheduling in home health care services, using a problem-specific knowledge-based artificial bee colony algorithm.
Alsabah et al. [11]	2021	6G wireless networks	Comprehensive Survey	Key enabling technologies for 6G networks while discussing the key technologies, potential applications, and challenges
Ghildiya et al. [12]	2023	6G in Industry 4.0	Comprehensive Survey	Examines the critical role of 6G communication in advancing Industry 4.0.
Moubayed et al. [13]	2022	Intelligent Automation in 6G Networks	Comprehensive Survey	Explores the end-to-end intelligent automation of 6G networks discussing the integration of AI and machine learning for automating network management and operations.
Banfaa et al. [14]	2023	6G Mobile Communication Technology	Comprehensive Survey	6G mobile communication technology, covering requirements, targets, applications (including industrial automation), challenges, advantages, and opportunities.
Fu et al., [8]	2021	Distributed Scheduling in Manufacturing	Comprehensive Survey	Distributed scheduling problems in intelligent manufacturing systems and various models and algorithms designed to optimize scheduling in smart factories.

TABLE 2
CAPABILITY COMPARISON OF 6G, 5G [7] AND CLASSICAL FIELD-LEVEL
COMMUNICATION BUSES.

Major Factors	6G	5G	Field-Level Bus (e.g., EtherCAT, ProfiNET)
Peak Data Rate	> 100 Gbps	10 (up to 20) Gbps	100 Mbps - 1 Gbps ⁵ [15]
UE Experience Data Rate	> 10 Gbps	> 1 Gbps	100 Mbps - 1 Gbps [15]
Traffic Density	> 100 Tbps/km ²	10 Tbps/km ²	N/A (Local Area Networks)
Connection Density	> 10 million/km ²	1 million/km ²	Up to thousands of nodes [16]
Delay	< 1ms	ms level	≈ 100 μs - 1 ms
Mobility	> 1000 km/h	> 350 km/h	Stationary or limited mobility
Spectrum Efficiency	> 3x to 5G	3x-5x to 4G	N/A (Wired)
Energy Efficiency	> 10x to 5G	1000x to 4G	Low power consumption [17]
Coverage Percent	> 99%	About 70%	Limited to the physical network layout
Reliability	> 99.999%	About 99.9%	99.999% (industrial environments) [18]
Positioning Precision	Centimeter Level	Meter Level	N/A
Receiver Sensitivity	< -130 dBm	About -120 dBm	N/A (Wired)

100 hensive survey to draw a picture of the 6G system in terms of drivers, use cases,
usage scenarios, requirements, KPI, architecture, and enabling technologies as
well as also their principles, advantages, challenges, and open research issues.
However, those survey papers only focuses on 6G systems. The authors in [20]
discuss specific TSN standards and projects in detail as well as their applicabil-
105 ity to various industries. On the other hand, this work is specific to TSN and
does not provide a broader view on industrial automation scenarios.

In contrast to the survey and review articles mentioned above, this paper
provides a comprehensive overview of the latest telecommunication solutions,
especially in the context of 6G networks, to drive the latest developments in
110 industrial automation. Despite the previous work on the potential applications
of telecommunication networks for industrial automation, there is still a lack
of a general overview of scenarios, requirements and challenges for emerging
telecommunication and network areas. In particular, it is unclear to practition-
ers, researchers, and developers in this emerging field what system specifications
115 are needed to support use cases, categories, and future directions. In this sur-
vey article, therefore, how industrial automation can be facilitated by advances
in telecommunications networks are explained. In the following sections, the
scenarios, requirements, challenges, and potential advancements pertaining to
communication for industrial automation are studied, with a particular empha-
120 sis on the role of 6G technology in addressing the evolving needs of Industry
4.0.

The roadmap of the survey can be summarized as follows: Section 2 provides
different industrial automation scenarios and use cases for industrial automation
in the context of 6G networks. Section 3 gives system requirements for industrial
125 automation in telecommunication networks. In Section 4, the challenges, lessons
learned and future directions for industrial automation in telecommunication
networks are discussed. Finally, our concluding remarks are provided in Section
5. Table 3 provides the notation table of the paper.

TABLE 3
LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Definition
4G	4th Generation
5G	5th Generation
6G	6th Generation
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
BCN	Blockchain Network
B5G	Beyond 5th Generation
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GPS	Global Positioning System
HD	High Definition
IAB	Integrated Access and Backhaul
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IoT	Internet of Things
IRS	Intelligent Reflective Surface
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
IVC	Immursive Virtual Communication
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
mMTC	massive Machine-Type Communications
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MR	Mixed Reality
NOMA	Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access
NPN	Non-Public Network
NR	New Radio
OT	Operation Technology
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
SIL	Safety Integrity Level
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SSI	Self Sovereign Identity
THz	Terahertz
TSN	Time Sensitive Network
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
uRLLC	ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication
WAN	Wide Area Network
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

2. Industrial Automation Categorizations and Use Cases

130 In this section, industrial automation categorization in 6G in Section 2.1 is presented first, then some reference industrial automation use cases are given in Section 2.2.

2.1. Industrial Automation Categorizations in 6G

While 5G can meet many of the communication requirements for industrial
135 automation, there are several scenarios where 6G is necessary to support the specific technical indicators of the communication requirements, such as ultra-low latency, extreme bandwidth, high density, high reliability and security. Industrial automation scenarios can be categorized under a variety of factors. In this survey paper, characteristics and properties of use cases and scenarios are
140 distinguished in the context of 6G networks.

1-) *Indoor & Outdoor categorization:* Factories, warehouses, and power plants are examples of indoor areas, while construction sites, manufacturing/process industries (such as the oil and gas industry), energy transport and distribution networks, and mixed indoor-outdoor environments such as harbors and smart-
145 grid substations are examples of outdoor areas for use cases. Indoor environments can facilitate the deployment of dedicated private networks independent of public networks.

2-) *Local, Multi-site, & Wide-area categorization:* Deployment use cases might cover a large range of geographic area, including numerous cities or nations, or
150 they may be limited to a specific area, such as a single city, region, or building. Private networks can be used in localized deployment scenarios to achieve this goal. On the other hand, network slicing of public networks is often the chosen option for deployments in a larger area. Local deployment scenarios involve the implementation of a network within a specific geographic area, such as a single
155 building, campus, or city. In these scenarios, private networks can be used to provide secure and reliable connectivity.

One example of a local deployment scenario is the optimization of water treatment and distribution systems within a single municipality. Another ex-

ample is the deployment of automated manufacturing and assembly line systems
160 in an industrial park. Local deployment scenarios are typically characterized by
their smaller scale and limited geographic area. In local deployment scenar-
ios, the implementation of a 6G network could enable manufacturers and other
industrial enterprises to optimize their processes, improve productivity, and re-
duce costs. For example, 6G networks could enable the deployment of highly
165 automated and intelligent assembly line systems that can communicate with
each other and adapt to changing production demands in real-time. This could
lead to more efficient and flexible manufacturing processes, reduced downtime,
and improved product quality. In addition, 6G networks could enable the de-
ployment of advanced robotics and autonomous systems that can work together
170 seamlessly in industrial settings. This could lead to increased safety, improved
precision, and reduced labor costs.

Multi-site deployment scenarios involve the implementation of a network
across multiple locations within a specific geographic area, such as a city or
region. These scenarios often require the use of a private network or a combi-
175 nation of private and public networks to ensure reliable and secure connectivity
between sites. When it comes to using multi-sites, there are several examples
that come to mind. For example, power generation and distribution systems
within a single city or region can benefit greatly from this type of deployment, as
highlighted in [21]. Similarly, water treatment and distribution systems within
180 a single municipality, as studied in [22], can also be optimized through the use
of several localized deployments. Another example is automated manufacturing
and assembly line systems in an industrial park, as described in a recent study
[23].

Multi-site deployment scenarios are typically characterized by their larger
185 scale and broader geographic area than local deployment scenarios. In multi-
site deployment scenarios, the implementation of a 6G network could enable
enterprises to connect and integrate their operations across multiple locations
in a seamless and efficient manner which could lead to improved collaboration,
better resource utilization, and increased agility. For example, 6G networks

190 could support the implementation of smart grids, which can optimize the distribution and management of energy resources. This could lead to more efficient and sustainable energy use, reduced energy costs, and improved reliability. 6G networks could also support the implementation of advanced logistics and supply chain management systems that can operate across multiple sites and enable
195 more efficient and responsive delivery of goods and services.

Wide-area deployment scenarios involve the implementation of a network across a large geographic area that may span multiple cities, regions, or even countries [24]. Wide-area deployment scenarios are typically characterized by their large scale and expansive geographic area. These scenarios often require
200 the use of public networks to provide effective and efficient connectivity. It may include, for example, the management of oil and gas pipelines across multiple countries. Another example of wide-area deployment is logistics and supply chain management across numerous warehouses or distribution sites. In both examples, the use of network slicing in open networks can increase effectiveness
205 and overall success.

In wide-area deployment scenarios, the implementation of a 6G network could enable enterprises to connect and manage their operations across vast distances and multiple locations in a highly efficient and secure manner. This could lead to improved collaboration, faster response times, and increased resilience. For example, in the case of managing oil and gas pipelines across
210 multiple countries, 6G networks could enable real-time monitoring and control of pipeline operations, including pressure, temperature, and flow rates. This could help to improve safety, reduce maintenance costs, and minimize the risk of pipeline leaks or spills. Furthermore, 6G networks could support the implementation of advanced logistics and supply chain management systems that
215 can operate across numerous warehouses or distribution sites. This could help to optimize transportation routes, reduce shipping times, and improve overall supply chain efficiency.

3-) *Communication service categories with IoT* : According to IMT-2020, 3GPP
220 and ITU in 5G standardization, eMBB, mMTC and uRLLC are three differ-

ent communication service categories. Cellular IIoT devices are any form of industrial equipment such as AGV that are equipped with various sensors (temperature, pressure, etc.). They can be of great use in many industries (e.g., consumer electronics, automotive, railway, construction, utilities (energy, gas), manufacturing, and transportation) and can be categorized in industrial automation IoT (to support collaborative robots, precise indoor positioning, or time synchronization for industry, e.g., to automate quality control processes on an assembly line in manufacturing automation or for power distribution), Critical IoT (such as AGV) in a warehouse, remote healthcare, or smart grids, Broadband IoT (such as some AR/VR apps, connected drones, wearables (e.g., smart watches, AR/VR goggles)) and massive IoT (such as logistics, tracking). Fig. 2 shows four broad categories of IoT segmentation where massive IoT category can be addressed by LTE-M and NB-IoT technologies [25]. Broadband IoT can be addressed by 5G NR. Critical IoT can be addressed by leveraging demanding uRLLC functionalities of B5G and 6G networks. Industrial automation IoT is addressed by Ethernet or TSN.

Figure 2: Cellular IoT segmentation for industrial automation.

Note that in industrial automation IoT, the deployment of 6G networks could enhance the capabilities of industrial automation IoT by providing higher data speeds, ultra-low latency, and increased device connectivity using technolo-

gies such as THz communication, AI-driven network optimization or advanced MIMO. In critical IoT applications, leveraging the demanding uRLLC functionalities of 6G networks using technologies such as TSN [26], IAB [27] or NOMA [28] could further improve the reliability and responsiveness of critical IoT applications. In broadband IoT, the introduction of 6G networks would further enhance the capabilities of broadband IoT, offering even faster speeds, lower latency, and more immersive experiences using technologies such as integrated satellite communication, IRS [29] or cell-free networks. In massive IoT, although existing technologies are sufficient for current massive IoT needs, 6G networks have the potential to provide enhanced connectivity, increased device density, and improved energy efficiency using technologies such as energy harvesting [30], ultra-narrowband communication [31] or hyper-dense networks [32], which would further benefit massive IoT applications.

4-) Private & Public MNO: In an IIoT use case, a private network operator may be established by an industrial end user or system provider. Private networks (also called NPN) provide services to an organization or group of organizations (e.g., a factory or construction site). This dedicated 6G IIoT system can be outsourced to external service providers such as mobile operators, service providers or integrators while relying on public carrier networks as well as enterprise IT networks (including commodity hardware and cloud-based applications).

In addition, a mobile network operator has the option to deploy a 6G IIoT system either fully or partially over the existing public network infrastructure. This decision depends on several factors, such as access to spectrum, coverage area, and the ability of the industrial enterprise to manage 6G communications services. Public networks tend to be more robust, use proprietary technologies, and are seamlessly integrated across multiple industries. As a rule of thumb, MNO tend to oversee infrastructure for remote outdoor and multi-layered environments, while industrial enterprises tend to use public networks only when reliability and accessibility are of paramount importance.

5-) Fixed & Temporary Deployments: IIoT use cases can be deployed either at fixed locations for a long time (e.g., factories, energy distribution networks,

ports, transportation infrastructure) or deployed temporarily (e.g., construction sites). Long-term deployments require fixed private or public 6G systems with long-term spectrum leases, SLA or equipment licenses, and may expand over time as use cases evolve. Temporary deployments, on the other hand, are flexible and dynamic network deployments based on techniques such as dynamic network slicing [33] or resource management and orchestration for performance and capacity improvements [34] and are based on local installations.

2.2. Reference Industrial Automation Use Cases

1-) *Electric Vehicles from a Smart Factory*: Smart factories should be transparent, efficient, connected and flexible through communication between machines, goods, logistics, people and processes throughout the lifecycle of a product. Therefore, meeting the communication requirements (e.g., between controllers, sensors, and servers) of the various services on the factory floor is a top priority. In this use case, after manufacturing resources and goods are delivered to a smart factory, intelligent smart forklifts are used to automatically stack items on high-bay racking. Later, RFID scanners are used to scan the delivered goods and identify individual parts and vehicle bodies. Then, smart autonomous factory trains are used to transport the required materials to the production line [35]. In this use case, AGV are used to transport the electric cars to be produced through the different production stages. Scanners at each station identify the parts of the vehicle on the assembly line, enabling the correct installation of the customized equipment. In this use case, communication between all machines and components is wirelessly connected, including individual tools such as networked torque wrenches (which prevent faulty assembly).

The characteristics of the applications in this use case include transparency, efficiency, connectivity, and flexibility, all of which are necessary for the smooth operation of a smart factory. Note that the communication requirements in the electric vehicles from smart factory pose a significant challenge, as there is a need for seamless and reliable communication between various machines, goods, logistics, people, and processes. Additionally, the use of wireless communication

in a factory environment introduces various difficulties such as interference, signal attenuation, and security issues. For machine systems like car area networks, hundreds of sensors may be needed to operate within a relatively small area, less than 100 meters. To ensure the proper functioning of these systems, the sensors
305 must communicate with extreme high reliability, and within a time frame of 100 microseconds⁶. The advantages of 6G technology in this use case include higher data transfer rates (e.g., with high frequency bands, such as THz and sub-terahertz (sub-THz)), ultra-low latency (e.g., with edge computing), and high reliability (e.g., through massive MIMO), which would enable the efficient
310 transfer of large amounts of data in real-time.

2-) Smart Construction Sites: IIoT devices, sensors, and automation are expected to be deployed on smart construction sites to improve safety, efficiency, and communication on construction sites. Drones and UAV can be used for surveying and mapping to create 3D models of the construction site and monitor
315 work in progress, soil conditions, volume of soil, etc. in real-time [36]. Wearable devices for workers can also be used to monitor the location, safety, and productivity of workers [37]. Smart construction sites have several characteristics that require reliable and fast communication. These sites involve a high level of automation with numerous IIoT devices, sensors, and drones. Real-time
320 data transmission is essential to ensure efficient coordination between machines, workers, and suppliers. However, communication in such environments is challenging due to various factors, including harsh outdoor conditions, interference from buildings and structures, and the need for high bandwidth to transmit large amounts of data.

325 With the advancements in 6G, these challenges can be addressed by providing higher data rates, low-latency, and better coverage (e.g., by utilizing a combination of different technologies, such as a higher number of antennas and beamforming, advanced signal processing techniques, and the use of higher

⁶Online: <https://www.nokia.com/about-us/newsroom/articles/6g-explained/>, Available: May 2023.

frequency bands such as THz frequencies) to support the connectivity needs
330 of smart construction sites. With 6G, construction companies can rely on ad-
vanced technologies such as augmented and virtual reality, real-time monitoring,
and automation for improved safety, efficiency, and productivity. For example,
maintenance workers can use AR glasses to access real-time data and instruc-
tions, reducing the need for on-site support and improving efficiency. More data
335 can be transmitted in real-time over 6G networks, e.g., HD video transmissions
from UAV and wearables on construction sites, which increases the level of
safety required. Overall, 6G can enable more reliable and efficient communica-
tion for smart construction sites, which will enhance the quality and speed of
construction projects.

340 *3-) Electrical Substations in Power Supply Networks:* In a digital substation,
digital devices such as protective relays, fault recorders, and programmable
logic controllers are used to distribute electrical power, transform voltages, con-
trol/redirect energy flows, or isolate network segments [38], as shown in Fig. 3.
Connecting these digital electronic devices (including sensors and communica-
345 tion devices, some of which may be local to the central control room and others
external) over 6G networks (with either full connectivity or wireless redundant
connectivity) can avoid the additional cost of wiring and improve flexibility
and resilience. 6G networks can improve protection (against cyber-attacks) and
control of electrical energy networks or power grid infrastructure by enabling
350 high-bandwidth and low-latency communications for data that must be trans-
mitted in real-time. Combined with AI-driven 6G networks, device failures can
be predicted and preventive maintenance can be enabled to reduce downtime.
IRS-based 6G networks can significantly improve communication quality while
reducing transmission power in energy infrastructures [29].

355 *4-) Real-time sensor-based Power Line Monitoring and Protection System:* In
this use case of smart grid line monitoring and protection, sensors are placed at
various locations along the power line to measure its electrical characteristics.
Two units monitor a power line (voltage and current) at different locations (e.g.,
via phasor measurement units) and compare measurements in real-time. When

Figure 3: An example of digital substation model.

360 the system detects abnormal behavior or faults (e.g., a surge or fault in the power line), it isolates the affected portion of the power line to prevent damage and minimize power supply interruptions [39].

The characteristics of the real-time sensor-based power line monitoring and protection system include the need for continuous and accurate monitoring of
 365 the power line’s electrical characteristics, rapid detection of faults or abnormal behavior, and isolation of affected portions of the power line to prevent damage and minimize power supply interruptions. In this use case, real-time communication between monitoring units is required, which can be up to 10s of km, with required latencies of a few milliseconds to detect and locate the
 370 exact fault point. This can help to fix the problem and restore power quickly. The difficulties of communication in this use case include the need for reliable and low-latency communication between monitoring units over long distances. Additionally, power lines can be subject to interference from various sources, including weather conditions, electrical noise, and other factors that can affect
 375 the accuracy of the monitoring data and the communication between monitoring units.

6G networks can provide significant advantages for this use case, including higher bandwidth and lower latency (e.g., by using advanced coding and mod-

ulation techniques to transmit information in short bursts with very low error
380 rates and very low latency), which can enable more accurate and efficient mon-
itoring of power lines. With 6G, it may be possible to monitor power lines in
real-time and quickly detect and isolate faults, reducing downtime and improv-
ing the reliability of power supply. 6G networks may also enable more efficient
use of resources, such as by optimizing the distribution of power to reduce waste
385 and improve overall system performance.

5-) Remote Control: This use case is for autonomous devices that require remote
communication when a task change is required. Multiple controllers for the
various devices/components on the PCB assembly lines can be used to remotely
control changes to the product or capture in-process data⁷. The use case begins
390 when a task change is required on a remote device. The controller sends a
request to the remote device, which responds with an acknowledgement. Once
the acknowledgement is received, the controller sends a new set of instructions
to the remote device. The remote device then executes the instructions and,
if successful, sends an acknowledgement back to the controller. The controller
395 will then update its status to reflect the task change. If the task change is
unsuccessful, the remote device sends an error message to the controller which
then handles the problem accordingly.

In this use case, the main characteristics of the application are remote con-
trol and real-time communication between the controllers and the autonomous
400 devices/components. The communication requirements for this use case include
low latency and high reliability (for mission-critical applications) to ensure that
the devices respond quickly and accurately to the controller's commands. Ad-
ditionally, the communication needs to be secure to prevent any unauthorized
access to the devices.

405 One of the difficulties of communication in this use case is the need for
reliable connectivity over long distances, as the devices may be located far away

⁷5GACIA, Key 5G Use Cases and Requirements: From the Viewpoint of Operational
Technology Providers, <https://bit.ly/3X9vvcg>

from the controller. This requires a network with a wider coverage area, such as a WAN, to ensure seamless communication. Another difficulty is the need for low latency, as any delay in communication could result in the device not responding
410 to the controller's commands in time, leading to errors or even accidents. In the context of 6G, the advantages of this use case can be improved by the higher data rates and lower latency offered by 6G networks. 6G's increased bandwidth and data rates can facilitate the transmission of large amounts of data in real-time, while the low latency can ensure faster response times for
415 the devices. 6G's low latency and high bandwidth can enable remote control of heavy machinery, such as excavators, cranes, and bulldozers. This can lead to improved control over the devices and faster execution of commands, resulting in increased efficiency, safety, cost-effectiveness and productivity by reducing the need for on-site operators.

420 *6-) Local Control:* This use case refers to cases where components of larger machines or multiple machines within a production building need to interact for a common task. For example, shuttle systems (automated storage and retrieval machines that transport materials within a single machine) have controllers that interact with robots or machines that require the precise position of the
425 shuttles in real-time [40] or collaborative small and autonomous devices that are part of an automated material-handling system targeted at pick-pack-and-ship warehouses [41]. In this use case, local communication between the controllers of the different machines is essential for coordination and synchronization. The communication between the components should be in real-time with very low
430 latency to avoid errors and collisions. Additionally, the communication should be reliable, with low packet loss, as even small errors can lead to significant problems in the production process.

With 6G, it is expected that higher bandwidth, lower latency, and better reliability (e.g., with network slicing to ensure that critical applications are given
435 priority access to network resources) can be achieved, which can improve the overall performance of the production process. The use of 6G can also lead to increased flexibility, allowing for more dynamic and agile production processes.

7-) *Reliable Connectivity on Factory Floor*: This use case ensures the safety of workers (to avoid injuries) and industrial machinery (to avoid interruptions or
440 breakdowns). For example, a light curtain system (consisting of a light beam between transmitter and receiver) periodically polls safety equipment to elicit a response within a specified time. If the response is delayed, the machine is disabled and placed in a safe state [42]. For the reliable connectivity on factory floor use case, the deployment of 6G networks can bring advantages
445 such as higher reliability, lower latency, and higher data rates e.g., through multiple wireless hops, device-to-device connections, simultaneous transmission and AI/ML. This can enable more real-time monitoring and control of machines and sensors, which can improve the overall efficiency and safety of the factory floor.

450 By integrating with other technologies, such as RFID and AGV, 6G can enable efficient and accurate management of inventory and equipment. However, communication on the factory floor can be challenging due to the presence of obstacles, high interference, and the need for low latency (on the order of sub-millisecond) and high reliability. 6G can address these challenges through the
455 use of higher frequency bands, massive MIMO, advanced antenna systems, and beamforming. Additionally, 6G can provide new capabilities such as holographic communications, which can enable workers to communicate and collaborate in a more immersive and efficient manner.

Finally, the relationship between the discussed use cases and deployment
460 scenarios is shown in Fig. 4. Note that the transition from wide-area outdoor environments to local and indoor scenarios typically involve demanding uRLLC requirements and requires the deployment of 6G private networks.

3. System Requirements

465 As the next generation of wireless communication networks, 6G is expected to provide faster speed, lower latency, higher capacity, greater bandwidth and wider range of services compared to 5G networks [43, 44, 7, 45]. Therefore, 6G

Figure 4: Relationship between use cases and deployments

has the potential to significantly advance industrial automation requirements, which demand high-performance networks for reliable communication among machines and devices and will be detailed in this section.

470 *3.1. Functional Requirements*

5G-ACIA (5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation) has studied vertical areas and their requirements [46]. According to 5G-ACIA, the following functional requirements are defined:

475 *(i) Operating in NPN* is necessary for network isolation. This enables total control of the industrial communication network while reducing interference from other networks.

(ii) Time Synchronization is quite critical due to the increased speed and complexity of industrial processes and the large number of connected devices. For instance, industrial communication networks require highly accurate time synchronization between the sync master and any sync device (on the order of ± 1 μ s).

480 *(iii) Integration with Existing Industrial Communication Networks* is the ACIA's

key requirement for 5G-enabled industrial networks that covers the ability to interface with existing industrial protocols, such as Profinet and Modbus, and
485 the ability to integrate with existing industrial control systems, such as SCADA systems.

(iv) *Support of Time-sensitive Networking (TSN)* can be designed to meet the strict timing requirements of industrial applications. This technology helps to ensure that industrial processes and applications operate in a highly synchro-
490 nized and deterministic manner, even in the presence of network congestion and other types of network disturbances.

(v) *QoS Monitoring* includes the ability to monitor key network parameters, such as latency, bandwidth, and jitter, and to identify and resolve any issues that may be impacting network performance.

495 (vi) *Positioning* refers to accurately determining the location of industrial devices, which is critical for many industrial applications, including asset tracking, logistics management, and industrial automation. The ACIA supports the use of GPS, in 5G-enabled industrial networks to ensure that these networks are able to provide the necessary levels of positioning accuracy and reliability.

500 3.2. Service Requirements and Performance Metrics

The requirements for communication services may vary depending on the type of traffic (periodic, aperiodic, non-deterministic, mixed) and the use cases considered (motion control, mobile robots, asset management of plant, etc.). Table 4 shows the requirements of wearables, industrial wireless sensors, and
505 video surveillance use cases⁸. 6G's higher frequency bands can provide greater bandwidth capacity, allowing for more users to access the network at once, as well as more data-intensive applications. Additionally, 6G's ability to support one microsecond latency communications and massive numbers of devices with ultra-low latency requirements can greatly enhance the speed and reliability of

⁸5G Americas, Becoming 5G-Advanced: the 3GPP 2025 Roadmap, <https://bit.ly/3H6rNuC>

510 industrial automation systems and enable real-time data processing and analysis [44].

The 3GPP has defined the requirements of cyber-physical control applications for automation in TS 22.104 [47]. In the 3GPP perspective on industrial automation, vertical domains and their corresponding sub-domains in industrial automation are described in [47] as Factories-of-the-Future (with sub-domains 515 factory automation, process automation, Human-Machine-Interfaces & production IT, logistics & warehouse and monitoring & maintenance), power distribution and smart-grid, central power generation, etc. A mapping of these domains to application areas is also given in Table A.2.1-1 of [47]. A detailed description of some emerging applications, their benefits, concepts, challenges, and 520 requirements of 6G is also provided in [45].

TABLE 4
REQUIREMENTS OF WEARABLES, INDUSTRIAL WIRELESS SENSORS, AND
VIDEO SURVEILLANCE USE CASES.

Use Case	Data Rate	Latency	Reliability	Battery
Wearables	5-50Mbps DL 2-5Mbps UL	Relaxed	N/A	Up to 1-2 weeks
Industrial Wireless Sensors	<2 Mbps	<100 ms	99.99 %	At least a few years
Video Surveillance	2-4 Mbps economic video 7.5-25 Mbps high-end video	<500 ms	99-99.9%	N/A

1-) *Communication System Availability and Reliability*: Most industrial sites tend to be 24/7 operational, so production and services continue throughout the year. Any interruption can result in financial (loss of sale, delivery penalties) and safety consequences. Some key performance metrics of a communication 525 service as defined in TS 22.104 are (i) communication service availability, (ii) communication service reliability, (iii) survival time, (iv) network mean time

between failures (MTBF), and (v) network mean time to repair (MTTR). The level of availability and reliability required is driven by business concerns, with
530 a trade-off between business-level loss (reputation, monetary, etc.) in the event of a system failure versus the additional complexity to increase availability, e.g., through redundancy improvements.

For example, as shown in Table 2, the 6G KPI service requirements demand for reliability greater than 99.999%. This is equivalent to no more than 0.001%
535 of 20 bytes packets can fail to be delivered less than 1 ms. In addition, the availability of communication service can be converted to network reliability based on survival time (the time a service can be maintained even if messages are occasionally not delivered within the specified latency limits) [48]. For example, a communication service availability of 99.9999% can be achieved with
540 a network reliability of 99.9% according to TS 22.104 [47]. The carrier-grade availability of 6G networks can be leveraged to provide high availability and pervasive monitoring for reliability.

2-) *Coverage*: Industrial sites are open and large spaces with high ceilings and large metal infrastructure. Therefore, intercell interference may occur in
545 such warehouses when radio antennas are installed in high ceilings to extend coverage. The heavy presence of metal infrastructure or equipment in indoor industrial scenarios can lead to blind spots for moving robots or AGV. For this reason, the 3GPP has developed an Indoor Factory (InF) channel model proposed in TR 38.901⁹ which focuses mainly on the presence of clutter (machinery
550 of different sizes, storage shelves, assembly lines) in factory floors. Site surveys can help reorganize the location of cellular radios to avoid complications that can block radio signals and disrupt cell coverage at industrial sites.

⁹(2022) Study on channel model for frequencies from 0.5 to 100 GHz (Release 17). [Online]. Available: <https://www.3gpp.org>

3.3. Non-functional Requirements:

1-) *Electromagnetic Compatibility of 6G*: EMC refers to the ability of electronic equipment to function without harmful EMI with other systems or devices. In industry, the radio equipment must function within the electromagnetic spectrum without interfering with other systems that could affect machine operation (e.g., AGV). Regulatory agencies (e.g., the Federal Communications Commission in the U.S and the ETSI in Europe) specify EMC requirements for cellular networks. 6G networks are expected to operate in the THz frequency range (0.1-10 THz) [49], requiring new methods to measure and mitigate interference for EMC assurance. New use cases in 6G are more stringent and require 6G devices that are more sensitive to interference. Therefore, EMC requirements, testing and compliance will likely continue to be one of the most important aspects of safely and reliably integrating 6G networks into industrial environments, depending on the country or region in which they operate.

2-) *Clean Room Certification*: Clean room certification refers to the process of certifying a manufacturing facility that meets certain standards (e.g., verifying that the room is free of contaminants during the semiconductor manufacturing process). Organizations that perform clean room certifications typically evaluated compliance with standards based on the ISO 14644 or Federal Standard 209E (U.S. Federal Standard). 6G networks, because of their potential use of wider and higher frequency bands (THz range), can be very susceptible to interference from particulate contaminants that could affect their functionality and performance. For this reason, 6G devices and equipment, and the industrial machines that work with them, should be manufactured in clean, certified environments.

3-) *Functional Safety*: This requirement is important in the context of 6G networks for mobile operators and OT companies. In any industrial communication system, safety functions such as emergency shutdown of a machine or reduction of speed for safety reasons (e.g., when an AGV detects a human in its path) are critical. 6G communication networks should support functional and machine safety requirements in industrial environments. ISO categorizes safety-

related standards into Type A (basic standard that applies to all machines) and
 585 Type B and C (both apply to specific types of machines)¹⁰. They describe the
 safety requirements for the functional safety of tools, machines and software.

For example, ISO 13849 is a Type B safety standard [50]. IEC 61508 is a
 global standard of the International Electrotechnical Commission that describes
 procedures for the design, deployment, and maintenance of safety-related auto-
 590 matic protection systems. Table 5 from IEC 61508 [51] shows the SIL values
 (a numerical rating system for defining the level of safety-related systems in in-
 dustrial process control and automation applications) as a function of the PFH.
 Failure probabilities can be used to evaluate the dependability of the system.
 SIL-2 indicates a lower level of safety integrity, while higher numbers indicate a
 595 higher level of safety integrity. A lower PFH indicates a lower risk of dangerous
 failure. Thus, a higher SIL indicates a more tolerable system. Fig. 5 shows a
 logical link in the safe communication channel that should not consume more
 than 1% of the maximum PFH values of the target SIL. For example, to achieve
 SIL-2 with a PFH of 10^{-6} , the failure rate at the logical link endpoints must
 600 not exceed 10^{-8} , i.e. extremely low failure probability [52].

TABLE 5
 FAILURE LIMITS FOR SAFETY INTEGRITY LEVELS IN A HIGH DEMAND OR
 CONTINUOUS MODEL.

Safety Integrity Level	Probability of Dangerous Failure per hour
4	$\geq 10^{-9} to < 10^{-8}$
3	$\geq 10^{-8} to < 10^{-7}$
2	$\geq 10^{-7} to < 10^{-6}$
1	$\geq 10^{-6} to < 10^{-5}$

4-) *Security (e.g. non-3GPP credentials)*: In the ACIA [46], security is seen
 as a critical aspect of 5G technology, especially when it comes to protecting sen-

¹⁰Online: <https://www.gt-engineering.it/en/Insights/le-norme-armonizzate-di-tipo-a-b-c-1-2-3>, Available: January-2023.

Figure 5: An example of functionally safe communication as part of the safety function.

sitive industrial data and networks from cyber threats such as hacking, malware, and data breaches. This can be accomplished through the implementation of various security measures, such as encryption, access control, and network segmentation. 6G is expected to introduce even more stringent security features, such as enhanced encryption algorithms, quantum-resistant cryptography, and robust authentication methods, to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of industrial data in an increasingly connected and data-driven landscape.

(5-) *Operations and Management* by vertical is a required functional component that provides secure, automated, and managed access for external applications to the services and operations of the G Alliance, which is introduced as a context for Connected Industries and Automation, Communication Service Interface/API by G Alliance. Finally, Table 6 summarizes the system requirements discussed in this section.

TABLE 6
SUMMARY OF 6G SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS.

Type	Description
Functional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — (1) Support for non-public networks (NPN) Time synchronization, — (2) Integration with existing industrial communication networks , (3) Support for time-sensitive networking (TSN), (4) QoS monitoring, (5) Positioning
Service Requirements and Performance Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Communication System availability and reliability, (2) Coverage
Non-functional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Electromagnetic compatibility, (2) Clean room certification, (3) Functional safety, (4) Security, (5) Operations and management

TABLE 7
SUMMARY OF RESEARCH ACTIVITIES AND RELATED WORKS IN COMMUNICATION FOR INDUSTRY AUTOMATION.

Research Activity	Description	Related Work
Categories	— Identifying design features relevant to the type of service.	[1], [21], [22], [23], [24]
	— Enhancements to support a robust automation network platform.	[7], [20]
	— Network connectivity with specified capabilities.	[25]
	— Serving solutions with installed base or simplifying the network complexity.	[2], [3]
	— Deployment schemes based on cost-efficiency and guaranteed availability.	[33], [34]
Use cases	— Monitoring the position of vehicles and tracking the material movement.	[35]
	— Optimizing efficiency by monitoring the progress and quality of the construction.	[36], [37]
	— Automated and intelligent substations that are operated and controlled remotely.	[38], [29]
	— Allowing the production, distribution and consumption of power for suppliers/consumers.	[39]
	— Providing remote control solution for users to access equipment in the environment.	[3], [34]
	— Performing local control at the point of sense without delay.	[40], [41]
	— Reliable solutions for improving occupational health and safety management.	[42]
	— Addresses the best possible functional requirements for Industrial applications.	[5, 46]
Requirements	— Investigating the specialized service and performance aspects.	[52], [47]
	— Defining the communication service availability and reliability.	[47], [48]
	— Coverage identification of the existing information on high frequencies.	3GPP TR38.901
	— Ensuring compliance of electromagnetic compatibility.	[49]
	— Verifying the room is free of contaminants during the semiconductor manufacturing.	ISO14644, FS209E
	— Requirements and guidance for the design/integration principles of safety-related parts.	[52], [50], [51]
	— Developing competence for next generation mobile technologies.	[43, 44, 53]
	— Ease of integration and standardization aspects.	[45, 54]
Lessons Learnt, Challenges & Future Directions	— Introduce new technologies to sustain the system and continue seamless operation.	[55], [56]
	— Recommendations for regulators and government agencies to determine spectrum.	[6, 27], [28]
	— Improving network connectivity and interface mitigation techniques.	[26, 30, 57, 58]
	— Enhancing security measures against quantum computing threats.	[59]
	— Integration with Blockchain for secure and reliable data preservation.	[60]
	— Decentralized digital identities for configuration and inventory management.	[61]

4. Lessons Learned, Challenges and Future Directions

Informed by the comprehensive exploration of research activities, use cases, and requirements in the preceding sections of literature, valuable lessons, identified challenges, and outlined future directions for communication in industrial automation are derived. These insights are grounded in the extensive body of related work and practical experiences discussed earlier. In this section, our findings, recommendations, and a forward-looking perspective on the evolution of communication technology in this context are presented. Lessons learned from the survey papers are presented in Section 4.1, then challenges in Section 4.2, and finally some directions for future research in Section 4.3.

4.1. Lessons Learned

Note that 6G is still in the research and development phase and it will some take time before it is available for commercial use in the use cases described above, e.g., construction sites or smart factories. At the same time, it is found that the use cases and requirements in industry are less mature when it comes to automation and digitization of complex industrial solutions (Section 2). In industrial automation, the deployment of wireless cellular networks, including technologies such as 4G and 5G, is advanced but not yet fully mature in all sectors (e.g., the full integration of wireless cellular networks for real-time control and monitoring in automation and robotics). Dependencies across all abstraction layers for production infrastructure automation and control using wireless cellular networks are still at an early stage.

The broad and diverse potential use of wireless spectrum in 6G (sub6 GHz, millimetre waves, and terahertz) is also a major concern when it comes to interoperability, compatibility and interference management of 6G devices with industrial machines. Moreover, autonomous applications require trustworthy and reliable data, operations, and decisions, which is still a concern in industry and is considered an active research area in the literature for industrial automation scenarios and requirements (Section 3). The effectiveness and real-world impact of these industrial production systems also depend on the presence

of human actors in such complicated production environments. Therefore, industrial automation scenarios have yet to address use cases related to trust in autonomous systems, human-robot collaboration, and explainable AI in 6G network-integrated environments of smart factories and industrial situations.

650 *4.2. Challenges*

(i) Extension to the Telecommunication Sector: There are many challenging use cases and requirements between ICT and industrial OT companies, where 6G could lead to a convergence of use cases. However, open, interoperable, and automated industrial applications for telecom networks have not yet been
655 sufficiently extended to end-to-end and vertical domains (including up to RAN) compared to extensions of enterprise IT environments. Unlike ICT, connectivity requirements of industry OT can vary widely (from high throughput to time-critical communications with battery constraints). Therefore, the development of scalable, interoperable and reliable connectivity platforms and frameworks
660 for industrial automation applications is still an ongoing research activity in this ecosystem.

(ii) Dynamic Environment: In industry, the industrial and network environment and system requirements change with space and time, requiring intelligent approaches that can adapt to these dynamics. Integrating this intelligence into
665 new hardware and software upgrades in the OT and ICT devices is a major challenge and further efforts should be made.

(iii) Support for Full Roaming/Mobility: Most private network deployed in industrial scenarios do not allow full mobility and roaming within industrial sites [58]. This may be acceptable for some manufacturing companies, but is not
670 sufficient, e.g., for logistics or transportation organizations. As a solution, coverage of private networks can be extended by public networks to allow full mobility/roaming for multiple SIM devices within industrial sites via flexible and comprehensive mobility and roaming architectures.

(iv) Device Availability and Compatibility: As cellular network technologies
675 evolve, it also becomes a challenge to build a device ecosystem for industrial

applications. For example, device chipsets should be supported not only devices in the by ICT ecosystem, but also by industrial OT devices of varying complexity on different spectrum bands. Moreover, devices should provide backward compatibility with previous generation devices that are already developed and
680 deployed in industrial sites.

(v) Integration with existing systems (Interoperability): As new technologies are introduced, there may be challenges related to interoperability, as different systems and devices may use different communication protocols or standards. Incorporating new technologies like AR/VR, mobile robots, XR, digital twin
685 and IVC into existing industrial automation systems can be challenging due to compatibility issues and the need to ensure seamless integration [54].

(vi) Safety: Industrial automation systems must adhere to strict safety standards, and incorporating new technologies can introduce additional safety concerns. For example, mobile robots may pose a hazard to workers if they are not
690 properly designed, operated, or maintained.

(vii) Security: As industrial automation systems become more connected and digitized with the increasing use of connected devices and systems, they become vulnerable to cyber threats and the risk of cyberattacks also increases. The use of AR/VR, mobile robots, XR, digital twin and IVC can increase the attack
695 surface of these systems, and additional security measures must be put in place to protect them. Security breaches can have serious consequences for industrial operations, so it's important to implement robust security measures to protect against threats.

(viii) Maintenance and repair: New technologies may require specialized skills
700 and knowledge to maintain and repair, which can be a challenge for organizations that do not have the necessary expertise in-house.

(ix) Cost: The adoption of new technologies can be expensive, and organizations must carefully evaluate the costs and benefits of incorporating them into their industrial automation systems.

705 *(x) Network congestion and interference:* As more and more devices and systems are connected to the network, congestion can become a significant issue,

potentially leading to delays, dropped connections, and other performance issues. Moreover, In industrial environments, there may be a lot of electromagnetic interference, which can affect wireless communication signals and lead to connectivity issues.

(xi) Data Privacy: With sensitive data being transmitted over communication networks, ensuring data privacy is critical. This can be especially challenging in the case of AR/VR technologies, which may require the transmission of large amounts of visual data.

(xii) Standardization: By following standardization principles and involving stakeholders from various domains, establishing robust global standards for 6G technology in the context of industrial automation is needed. These standards will not only ensure interoperability but also foster innovation, drive economic growth, and enhance the efficiency and safety of industrial processes.

(xiii) Sustainable operations: Maintaining low power consumption for high-performance network devices in industrial automation can be a challenge. Industry best practices, policies, and regulations can play an important role in promoting and incentivizing the adoption of sustainable and energy-efficient industrial automation operations.

(xiv) Spectrum allocation: It is anticipated that the latest primary frequency ranges for 6G will be allocated as mid-bands from 7 to 20 GHz for outdoor cells in urban areas (to allow for increased capacity with the use of extreme MIMO technology); low bands ranging from 460 to 694 MHz (for exceptional coverage), and sub-THz frequencies (for peak data rates surpassing 100 Gbps)¹¹. However, efficient allocation of THz frequency bands is still under investigation especially in industrial environments.

(xv) Large scale operations: Industrial systems are often large-scale operations with numerous devices, sensors and machines distributed over wide areas. Managing such a dispersed network of devices can be a challenge, especially

¹¹Online: <https://www.bell-labs.com/institute/blog/6g-eras-enormous-capacity-demands-will-require-new-spectrum-and-extreme-massive-mimo/>, Available: May 2023.

735 when real-time data collection and processing is required.

(ix) *Uncertainties in industrial systems*: In industrial environments, especially in critical processes, uncertainties such as equipment failures, process variations, unpredictable machine failures, supply chain disruptions or unexpected changes in demand can disrupt operations and lead to costly downtime and inefficiencies. Traditional approaches that already exist in the industry may 740 not be sufficient to address these issues preemptively and may not provide the reliability and speed required to respond effectively to such disruptions.

4.3. Future Directions

(i) *Quantum Communication* can improve the security, dependability, and speed 745 of communication between industrial machines and sensors. This might lessen the possibility of cyberattacks, boost the accuracy and speed of data flow, and make real-time data more accessible to stakeholders. However, real use cases are in general missing in today's industrial applications. Further studies are needed on developing practical use cases for quantum computing and cryptography 750 in industrial automation and the emerging paradigms of quantum computing (QC), Quantum ML (QML) for predictive maintenance and optimization of manufacturing and communication processes, and post-quantum cryptography (PQC) in the field of industrial automation [59] as well as investigating the feasibility and efficiency of implementing quantum key distribution (QKD) in 755 communication between industrial machines and sensors.

(ii) *Blockchain Networks* can provide a highly available, robust, and tamper-proof system while eliminating single point of failure. These networks can be used in the industrial sector from the perspective of manufacturing system and product life cycle management [60], energy sector (peer-to-peer energy trading, 760 smart grid) or metrology. Existing business scenarios in industrial networks should be extended to include BCN, taking into account the emergence of 6G networks to enhance the reliability and performance of industrial communication systems. More focus can be on the development of robust and scalable protocols for smart contract execution, data sharing, and secure communication when

765 integration of blockchain technology into existing industrial networks.

(iii) *SSI* technology, which provides blockchain-based distributed digital identity, can enable greater transparency over the digital identities of industrial assets (e.g., for IIoT devices [61]). In this way, decentralized digital identities can be created for the purposes of authentication, verification, and authorization, e.g., for remote control of such industrial devices, thus avoiding centralized identity management systems (which are single-point-of failure) and bringing scalability and efficiency to the industrial manufacturing process. Future research can explore the integration of decentralized digital identities into industrial automation systems, focusing on the development of practical solutions for identity verification and authentication in distributed manufacturing systems. Topics such as the use of SSI for secure remote control of industrial devices and the potential benefits of using SSI in conjunction with blockchain networks to enhance the security and privacy of industrial data can be further elaborated.

(iv) *Industry 5.0 and the Factory of the Future:* are expected to leverage emerging technologies such as 6G networks, AI, and robotics to create a more sustainable and socially responsible manufacturing industry. The widespread adoption of 6G will further drive progress toward Industry 5.0. By co-developing communications and control in 6G networks, it will be possible to reduce costs, increase data rates, and expand the number of potential use cases in industrial automation. Joint communication, sensing, and localization will meet industry needs for a single system. 6G could also enable the deployment of new zero-energy or battery-less devices through backscatter communications [57] and the use of mobile robot swarms and drones [53]. Additionally, a significant increase in data collection for analytics and closed-loop control, teleoperation and telepresence in industrial automation scenarios [55], high precision remote control of machines and robots, enhanced human-machine interaction such as haptic feedback and AR/VR interfaces to improve the efficiency and safety of industrial processes [56] are also expected with 6G.

(v) *Integration of 6G communication technology with renewable energy systems,* such as solar and wind power, to create more energy-efficient and sustain-

able industrial processes.

Finally, see Table 7 for a summary description of the industry automation research activities in the area of communications and related work covered in this survey.

800 **5. Conclusion**

The convergence of telecommunications and industry is leading to new use cases and requirements as network operators, vendors, and industrial companies work together to enable industrial applications such as mobile robots, AGV, or immersive AR/VR applications in their infrastructure. In this paper, the categorizations, use cases and requirements for industrial automation are investigated 805 from the perspective of 6G communications. At the end of the paper, lessons learned, challenges and future directions for the convergence of industrial automation with 6G are outlined. We believe that exploring robust, flexible, and secure cellular connectivity in the context of industrial automation is an ongoing 810 endeavor. Considerable efforts are therefore still needed to improve the use of such systems in practice.

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